

The Effect of Locus of Control, Work Environment, and Work Conflict on Employee Performance at Bank Central Asia in Solo

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Abstract: This study aims to analyze the influence exerted by locus of control, work environment, and work conflict on employee performance. The sample used in this study was at Bank Central Asia (BCA) Kcu Solo by taking a sample of 48 employees and divided into 4 statements according to the variables. Sampling technique with purposive sampling method using SPSS version 25.0. The results showed that locus of control had an effect on the performance of BCA Kcu Solo employees. In addition, the work environment also affects employee performance. However, the results of the study are 1. Locus of control has a positive and significant effect on BCA employee performance, 2. The work environment has a positive and significant effect on BCA employee performance, 3. Work conflict has no effect on BCA employee performance.

Keywords: Employee Performance, Locus of Control, Work Environment, Work Conflict.

I. INTRODUCTION

Frequent changes in technological developments within companies can lead to competitive competition between employees, in terms of achieving performance in realizing goals, vision and mission in the composition of an organization, employee performance can affect the company in the productivity of a company if employee performance is not good then it has a negative impact on company assessment, if the employee's performance is good, it will affect the quality of the company and there are several factors that affect employee performance, namely locus of control (self-control), work environment and work conflict. If one of these factors is a failure, human resources in the company will decrease.

According to Wayan Wiriani et.al. (2013), employee performance can be influenced by individual factors, including locus of control, which is a personality that refers to self-control and training relationships with employees. Rotter (1973) and Owie (1978) in Karwono et al (2007) revealed that the orientation of the locus of control possessed by students was positively correlated with the learning achievement achieved. Someone who has an internal locus of control has a tendency to be more active in seeking, processing and utilizing various information, and has intrinsic motivation to achieve high, so that he will have a greater opportunity to achieve better than those who have an external locus of control.

There are related studies, namely locus of control is divided into 2 types, namely internal locus of control is the behavior of employees who tend to be positive and optimistic while external locus of control is the behavior of employees who tend to be negative and resigned to everything. Management of emotions that regulate when humans are hit by sadness that can damage the mind logically, Emotions are said to be managed successfully if they are able to console themselves when they are overwritten by sadness in order to release anxiety, moodiness, resentment and get back on their feet (Melandy and Aziza, 2006).

The work environment is divided into two, namely the physical work environment, namely physical conditions, and the non-physical work environment, namely conditions related to work relationships between superiors and fellow co-workers or subordinates (Sedarmayanti, 2011: 26). All tools or materials in the surrounding environment can affect individuals in their performance (Mangkunegara, 2017)

Unfair competition based on ambition and emotional attitude in obtaining victory. The old view considers conflict within the organization as a negative thing that leads to divisions in agencies, therefore it must be eliminated because it hinders optimal performance and disputes are considered an indication that something is wrong with the organization and that means organizational rules are not being implemented (Hasibuan 2008: 199)

Emotional management, which means handling feelings so that they can be expressed properly, is a skill that relies heavily on self-awareness. Emotions are said to be managed successfully if they are able to cheer themselves up when overwritten by sadness so they can let go of anxiety, moodiness, offense and bounce back quickly from all of that. Self-control can be called human emotions or feelings that govern when humans are hit by sadness which can damage the mind logically (Melandy and Aziza, 2006).

PT Bank Central Asia is the largest private company and is engaged in the banking sector, the problems faced by BCA are in the performance of employees with work conflicts. Based on the results of a pre-survey conducted through interviews with several employees, it is known that there are several problems that occur causing a decrease in performance employees due to increased work conflict at PT BCA. The performance indicators and standards set in measuring employee performance are the problems found in declining employee performance, namely locus of control, work environment, and work conflict. Several indicators in measuring employee performance at PT BCA do not go well, this is because by several factors.

Based on the results of a questionnaire survey with PT BCA employees in the work process. This is due to the very high individualism attitude, so that the performance is not productivity oriented. Another problem is that there are still leaders who are less sensitive to their employees.

PT BCA Tbk was selected as the research sample based on considerations regarding different policies among employees and continuously conducting PT BCA questionnaire surveys on its employees. Previous research has never used, work environment, and work conflict. Therefore, this study intends efforts within the company to reduce work conflict which aims to improve employee performance in a company.

Based on the description of the background, the problems in this study are formulated as follows:

1. Does Locus of Control affect the performance of Kcu BCA employees in Solo?
2. Does the work environment affect the performance of Kcu BCA employees in Solo?
3. Does work conflict affect the performance of Kcu BCA employees in Solo?

Based on the description of the problem formulation, the purpose of this study is as follows:

1. To test and analyze the effect of Locus of Control on the performance of Kcu BCA employees in Solo.
2. To test and analyze the influence of the work environment on the performance of Kcu BCA employees in Solo.
3. To test and analyze work conflict in the performance of Kcu BCA employees in Solo.

This research is expected to provide theoretical and practical benefits, namely to contribute to the development of science in general and the fields of management accounting and behavioral accounting, especially for those who wish to study self-control on locus of control, work environment, work conflicts to improve performance, and it is hoped that able to be used as material for consideration or input to the company in improving employee performance.

The main purpose of employee performance is to motivate employees to achieve company goals in accordance with company behavior standards in order to achieve the expected results. Employee performance appraisal is useful for reducing the existence of inappropriate attitudes and behaviors and growing and implementing the desired behavior with timely feedback from performance rewards. The research results of Princess Elviana et al. variable work environment, work motivation, TPP have a positive and significant impact on employee performance.

1.1 Literature review

1.1.1 Locus of control(X1)

Self-control is the management of emotions which means handling feelings so that they can be expressed properly, this is a skill that is very dependent on self-awareness. Emotions are said to be

managed successfully if they are able to cheer themselves up when overwritten by sadness so they can let go of anxiety, moodiness, offense and bounce back quickly from all of that. Self-control can be called human emotions or feelings that govern when humans are hit by sadness which can damage the mind logically (Melandy and Aziza, 2006). *Locus of control* including part of the individual's personality and beliefs that control his life, locus of control (self-control) is individual responsibility for all aspects inside and outside control of himself and is divided into two, namely internal locus of control has better behavior and tends to be positive rather than an external locus of control, in theory and what happens in the field locus of control allows employee behavior when in a conflict situation to be influenced by the characteristics of the internal locus of control.

1.1.2 Work environment (X2)

The work environment is the whole of the tools and materials faced by the surrounding environment where a person works, his work methods and work arrangements both as individuals and groups, from the conclusion above, the work environment can affect a person's performance (Mangkunegara, 2017). The work environment is divided into two, namely the physical work environment is all physical conditions that exist around the workplace that can affect employees both directly and indirectly, non-physical work environment are all conditions that occur related to work relationships, relationships with superiors and relationships colleagues, or relationships with subordinates. (Sedarmayanti, 2011:26).

1.1.3 Work Conflict (X3)

Work conflict is unhealthy competition based on ambition and emotional attitude in gaining victory. The old view considers conflict within the organization as a negative thing that leads to divisions in agencies, therefore it must be eliminated because it hinders optimal performance (Hasibuan, 2008: 199). Conflict within the organization is unavoidable and its presence magnifies the problem and knowing organizational deficiencies against weaknesses can lead to organizational goals and will have an impact on organizational performance. Conflict is a dispute between two parties that intentionally or unintentionally triggers disputes, competition between company employees. Conflicts must be prevented and resolved as early as possible so that good cooperation is maintained in order to avoid tension and division among fellow employees. Healthy competition must always be created and fostered so that organizational dynamics, creativity, self-introspection, self-development, work morale and employee work productivity increase so that company, employee and community goals are achieved (Hasibuan, 2013: 201).

1.1.4 Employee Performance (Y)

Employee performance is a product of time and opportunities to pursue these opportunities is nothing and the time that we do not have that does not provide opportunities even has a little behavioral value is someone who is involved in carrying out the life and activities of organizations both business and public organizations (Gilbert, 1978) . an organization has human resources who have high responsibility, high morale, reliable law, it is certain that the organization will improve good performance (Sutrisno, 2010).factors that influence employee performance such as knowledge, technicality, dependence on other people, policies, employee abilities, attendance, leadership and even interest that will make employees have the will to improve their performance properly and with quality. Quality employee performance is due to the ability, communication, and work skills of employees, in an effort to improve better work results, a performance appraisal is needed, which is a process used by companies to evaluate employee performance. Company employees try to plan, organize and carry out the work for which they are responsible, the responsibilities of employees at work will have a positive impact on improving performance if employees do all their work well(Damayanti, 2013).

1.2 Hypothesis

Research conducted by Wayan Wiriani et al. (2013) found that internal locus of control and external locus of control are significant for employee performance. Some of the research results above the interaction effect or joint effect between training and locus of control on performance is significant. This means that there is a joint effect between the level of training and the level on performance. The performance score of the internal locus of control level group of employees with a high training frequency shows the highest performance achievement score significantly. conversely the group of external employees with low training frequency shows the lowest performance achievement. Thus the hypothesis that can be put forward is:

H1: Self-control (Locus Of Control) affects employee performance.

Research conducted by Eldaa cintia et al. (2016) the results of the discovery that the physical and non-physical work environment are significant on employee performance, the results of the research above it can be stated that it is suspected that there is a positive and significant influence between the physical and non-physical work environment on employee performance, simultaneous test shows that the physical and non-physical work environment has a significant influence on employee performance by 72.1%, the results show that both partially and simultaneously the physical work environment and non-physical work environment have a significant influence on employee performance. Thus the hypothesis that can be put forward is:

H2: The work environment influences employee performance.

Research conducted by Ilham Syuhasa et al. (2021) the findings show that the variables work conflict and work morale partially have a positive and significant effect on employee performance, work conflict variables partially have a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Angkasa Pura II Kuala Namu Avsec Division that the Work Morale variable partially has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Angkasa Pura II Kuala Namu Avsec Division indicates that the work conflict and work morale variables are simultaneous positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Avsec Division of Angkasa Pura II Kuala Namu. Thus the hypothesis that can be put forward is:

H3: Work conflict affects employee performance.

II. HEADINGS

This study uses field research (field research) information obtained directly from employee respondents at PT Bank Central Asia Kcu in Solo.

2.1 Research design or type of research

This research is a quantitative research using primary data because it leads to calculations in the form of numbers and data analysis, and uses field research types of information obtained directly from PT Bank Central Asia Kcu employee respondents in Solo using a questionnaire method in data collection.

2.2 Population, sample, and sampling technique

The population used in this study were 48 employees of Bank BCA (Bank Central Asia) Kcu in Solo using a questionnaire as measured by a Likert scale. As well as the selection of samples used in this study is probability sampling.

The simple random sampling technique is a sampling technique from members of the population which is carried out randomly without regard to the existing strata in the population, this technique can be done if the population is homogeneous.

2.3 Data collection technique

The data used in this study are primary data and were obtained by distributing questionnaires to employees of Bank BCA Kcu Solo at the time they were submitted. The questionnaire contains questions to obtain information about locus of control (self-control), work environment, work conflicts, employee performance.

2.4 Operational definition and measurement of variables

There are several independent variables in this study, namely locus of control, work environment, work conflict. The definitions of the variables along with the measurements used are as follows:

2.4.1. Locus Of Control(Self-control)

Individuals feel confident to solve all the problems they face in every job they are charged (Soraya Eka, 2010). This variable is measured by the following indicators:

Internal locus of control indicators have the following characteristics:

1. Likes to work hard
The individual is optimistic and accepts all suggestions without exception.
2. Have initiative
Individuals take the initiative and comply with applicable regulations.
3. Always trying to find a solution

Individuals always provide ideas and solutions to achieve goals.

4. Think effectively

Individual ability to think effectively in completing tasks.

5. Have the perception that effort must be made if you want to succeed. Perception of employees in trying to achieve goals.

External locus of control indicators have the following characteristics:

1. Lack of initiative

Individuals believe in instinct will make things easier.

2. Quitter

Individuals have selfish nature.

3. It's easy to overlook something

Individuals believe connection and luck influence one's performance.

4. Lack of searching for information

Individuals believe what is believed rather than current information.

5. Easily influenced by someone

Individuals prefer to follow their co-workers

2.4.2. Work environment

The work environment is a workplace situation that creates employee comfort and safety (Subroto, 2005).

This variable is measured by work environment indicators which are divided as follows:

Physical work environment indicators are:

1. Lighting

The importance of light to support employee performance.

2. air circulation

The importance of air exchange for the comfort of the surrounding environment.

3. Noise

The importance of soundproof rooms in reducing noise.

4. environmental Hygiene

The importance of maintaining cleanliness to support the surrounding environment.

5. job security

The importance of keeping the surrounding environment safe.

6. Color layout

The importance of color selection to increase serenity.

7. Spatial

The importance of maintaining spatial layout affects the comfort of the mood.

Non-physical work environment indicators are:

1. Working relationship between superiors and subordinates

Company leaders are required to maintain relationships and always be fair in all respects in order to create a fair atmosphere for fellow employees.

2. Relations between fellow employees

Employees are required to help each other in order to create a good relationship.

2.4.3. work conflict

An interactive process in the mismatch in the organization (M. Afzalur Rahim, 2011:16). This variable is measured by the following indicators:

1. Differences in goals and perceptions

Differences of opinion among employees in goals.

2. Causes of conflict between employees

Differences of opinion and solutions in solving problems between employees.

3. Causes of staff conflict with the unit head (line staff conflict)

Causes of conflict between unit leaders and staff in excess of authority.

4. Causes of functional conflict

Causes of Conflict support the achievement of group goals and improve group performance (different divisions).

There is a dependent variable in this study, namely employee performance. The definitions of the variables along with the measurements used are as follows:

2.4.4. Employee performance

The level of success of a person in carrying out work is called the level of performance, in general performance is defined as a person's success in carrying out his work (Nurhayati, 2003). This variable is measured by the following indicators:

1. Work quality
The ability of employees to follow applicable procedures.
 2. Working quantity
Employee perception of the amount earned.
 3. Punctuality
Individual confidence in doing work on time.
 4. effectiveness
Perception of employees in using resources effectively.
 5. independence
Perception of employees in assessing and completing their own performance.
- In this study using a Likert scale measurement using 5 point skills, namely:

Table 1
Likert scale

No	Answer	Code	Score Value
1	Strongly agree	SS	5
2	Agree	S	4
3	Neutral	N	3
4	Don't agree	TS	2
5	Strongly Disagree	STS	1

III. INDENTATIONS AND EQUATIONS

The data analysis method used is multiple linear regression analysis, according to the formulation of the problem and the purpose of the hypothesis proposed in this study. After all the data has been collected, data analysis will then be carried out consisting of:

3.1 Test instrument data

Distribution of questionnaires in the form of questions answered by respondents such as name, age, gender, last education and length of work and research topics. Instrument test includes:

3.1.1 Validity test

The validity testing technique uses the Bivariate Pearson correlation. This item has a significant correlation with a valid score. Sugiyono (2018), if $r_{count} \geq r_{table}$ (2-tailed test with sig. 0.05) is declared valid. The correlation method used to test the validity of this study is the Pearson product moment correlation with the following formula

$$\frac{n(\sum xy) - (\sum x \sum y)}{\sqrt{(n\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2)(n\sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2)}}$$

r_{xy} = correlation coefficient

n = number of respondents

x = Look for a place statement

y = statement item total score

$\sum x$ = total score of statement items

$\sum y$ = the sum of the total score of the items turns out

$\sum xy$ = the number of x and y multiplications

3.1.2 Reliability test

The reliability test in this study is used to measure the statistical approach, through the reliability coefficient and if the reliability coefficient is greater than 0.06 then overall the statement is declared reliable. The high or low reliability is close to number 1, the value is > 0.7 , then the reliability is sufficient, while if the alpha is > 0.7 , the item is consistently reliable.

3.2 Classic assumption test

The classical assumption test is carried out to ensure that the model is validated free from assumption deviations so that the OLS linear regression requirements are met, the classic assumption test is:

3.2.1 Data normality test

The normality test aims to test a regression model of the independent and dependent variables, the research criteria are said to be normal if Asymp. Sig (2-tailed) residual variable is above 0.05 or 5%, .Sig.(2-tailed) > 0.05 . Conversely, if it is below 0.05 or 5%, Sig.(2-tailed) < 0.05 the data is not normally distributed or does not meet the normality test.

3.2.2 Heteroscedasticity test

The heteroscedasticity test aims to test the dissimilarity of the variance of one model to another. The decision making criterion is if the significance value (sig) > 0.05 , then the conclusion is that heteroscedasticity does not occur, but if the significance value (sig) < 0.05 , then heteroscedasticity occurs

3.2.3 Multicollinearity test.

The multicollinearity test aims to examine the correlation between independent variables. The cutoff value used is the tolerance value of 0.10 if the VIF value < 10 is declared to pass multicollinearity while the VIF value > 10 is declared not to pass multicollinearity with a value of > 0.8

3.3 Hypothesis testing

The hypothesis test in this study is multiple linear regression analysis, namely:

3.3.1 Multiple linear regression analysis

Multiple linear regression analysis which aims to examine the effect of one variable on another, can be formulated as follows:

$$KK = \alpha + \beta_1. LOC + \beta_2. L + \beta_3. KOK$$

KK =employee performance

α = constant coefficient

$\beta_1\beta_2\beta_3$ = regression coefficient

LOC = locus of control

LK = work environment

HOW COME = work conflict

3.3.2 F test

The F test is used to determine the effect of the independent variable (X) on the dependent (Y) using the ANOVA model. The decision making criterion is if the significance value (sig) < 0.05 means that the hypothesis is accepted. This means that the independent variable (X) simultaneously (simultaneously) influences the dependent variable (Y), but if the significance value (sig) > 0.05 means that the hypothesis is accepted. This means that the independent variable (X) simultaneously (simultaneously) influences the dependent variable (Y).

3.3.3 Test R2 (Coefficient of determination)

This test is to measure the effect of the size of the independent variable on the dependent variable, the criteria in testing the coefficient of determination is if the magnitude of the coefficient of determination (R2) lies between 0 and 1 or 0% to 100% there is a positive influence and correlation between variables otherwise if $R^2 = 0$ then no there is a correlation between the variables tested.

3.3.4 T test

The t test is used to show the effect of one independent variable individually in explaining the dependent variable, while the criteria of the T test are if the significance value (sig.) < 0.05 then the independent variable affects the dependent

variable, conversely if the significant value is > 0.005 then the independent variable is significantly significantly does not affect the dependent variable.

IV. FIGURES AND TABLES

4.1 Findings

This research is a quantitative research using primary data from distributing questionnaires to employees of Bank Central Asia Solo

4.1.1 Validity test

Validity test is intended to see how far the accuracy of a measuring instrument used in research in carrying out its functions. The statement can be said to be valid if $r_{count} > r_{table}$ and significance value < 0.05 . The results of the validity test of the questions on each variable are presented in the table below:

Table 2

Declaration Number	Count	Rtable	Information
LOC. 1	0.609	0.320	Valid
LOC. 2	0.544	0.320	Valid
LOC. 3	0.574	0.320	Valid
LOC. 4	0.382	0.320	Valid
LOC. 5	0.571	0.320	Valid
LOC. 6	0.509	0.320	Valid
LOC. 7	0.561	0.320	Valid
LOC. 8	0.203	0.320	Invalid
LOC. 9	0.530	0.320	Valid
LOC. 10	-0.169	0.320	Invalid

Locus of Control Validity Test Results

Source: Primary data processed, 2022

Based on the results of testing the validity of statements for locus of control variables, it is known that statement items number 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7 and 9 are valid because $r_{count} > r_{table}$. However, statement items number 8 and 10 are invalid because $r_{count} < r_{table}$ so these items are deleted and not used in the next test.

Table 3

Work Environment validity test results

Declaration Number	Count	Rtable	Information
LK.1	0.649	0.320	Valid
LK.2	0.512	0.320	Valid
LK.3	0.452	0.320	Valid
LK.4	0.399	0.320	Valid
LK.5	0.368	0.320	Valid
LK. 6	0.554	0.320	Valid
LK. 7	-0.203	0.320	Invalid
LK. 8	0.599	0.320	Valid
LK. 9	0.509	0.320	Valid
LK. 10	0.480	0.320	Valid

Source: Primary data processed, 2022

Based on the results of testing the validity of statements for work environment variables it is known that all statement items number 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 8, 9 and 10 are valid, this can be seen from the value of $r_{count} > r_{table}$. Meanwhile, statement item number 7 was declared invalid because $r_{count} < r_{table}$ and could not be used for further testing.

Table 4
Work Conflict Validity Test Results

Declaration	Count	Rtable	Information
Number			
KOK. 1	0.594	0.320	Valid
KOK. 2	0.591	0.320	Valid
KOK. 3	0.584	0.320	Valid
KOK. 4	0.563	0.320	Valid
KOK. 5	0.299	0.320	Invalid
KOK. 6	0.384	0.320	Valid
KOK. 7	0.680	0.320	Valid
KOK. 8	0.609	0.320	Valid
KOK. 9	0.532	0.320	Valid
KOK. 10	-0.061	0.320	Invalid

Source: Primary data processed, 2022

Based on the results of testing the validity of statements for work conflict variables, it is known that statement items number 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 8 and 9 are valid, this can be seen from the value of $r_{count} > r_{table}$. However, statement items number 5 and 10 are known to be invalid because $r_{count} < r_{table}$, so they must be deleted and not used in the next test.

Table 5

Employee Performance Validity Test Results

Declaration Number	Count	Rtable	Information
KK. 1	0.612	0.320	Valid
KK. 2	0.728	0.320	Valid
KK. 3	0.410	0.320	Valid
KK. 4	0.405	0.320	Valid
KK. 5	0.549	0.320	Valid
KK. 6	0.468	0.320	Valid
KK. 7	0.692	0.320	Valid
KK. 8	0.535	0.320	Valid
KK. 9	0.728	0.320	Valid
KK. 10	0.386	0.320	Valid

Source: Primary data processed, 2022

Based on the results of testing the validity of statements for employee performance variables, it is known that all statement items are valid, this can be seen from the value of $r_{count} > r_{table}$.

4.1.2 Normality test

The normality test in this study used the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. The data is said to be normally distributed if the significance value is > 0.05 .

Table 6
Normality Test Results

Variable	Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z	Sig.	Conclusion
Unstandardized Residuals	0.076	0.200	Data is normally distributed

Source: Primary data processed, 2022

Based on the results of the normality test, it is known that the probability value is > 0.05 , therefore the data in this study are declared to be normally distributed.

4.1.3 Heteroscedasticity Test

The heteroscedasticity test in this study was carried out using the Spearman Rho test. The regression model is declared free from heteroscedasticity problems if the value is sign. >0.05 .

Table 7
Heteroscedasticity Test Results

Variable	Sig. (P-Value)	Conclusion
Locus of Control	0.765	There is no heteroscedasticity
Work environment	0.948	There is no heteroscedasticity
Work Conflict	0.945	There is no heteroscedasticity

Source: Primary data processed, 2022

Based on the results of the heteroscedasticity test in table IV.14 it is known that the significance of each variable is greater than 0.05. This shows that in this study there was no problem of heteroscedasticity.

4.1.4 Multicollinearity Test

The multicollinearity test aims to test and find out whether there is a correlation in a regression model. The regression model can be said to be free from multicollinearity if the TOL value is > 0.01 and the VIF value is <10 .

Table IV.15
Multicollinearity Test Results

Variable	TOLL	VIF	Conclusion
Locus of Control	0.479	2,087	No multicollinearity
Work environment	0.492	2,033	No multicollinearity
Work Conflict	0.963	1.039	No multicollinearity

Source: Primary data processed, 2022

Based on the results of the multicollinearity test presented in the table above, it is known that the regression model in this study is free from multicollinearity symptoms. This is indicated by the TOL value > 0.01 and the VIF value < 10 .

4.1.5 Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Test

Multiple linear regression analysis is intended to examine the effect of the relationship between the independent variables on the dependent variable

Table 9

Test	Test Variable	Test results
T test	Locus Of Control	3,720
	Work environment	4,848
	Work Conflict	-2,001
	F test	42,603
Coefficient of Determination (R2)		0.883

Source: Primary data processed, 2022

Based on the output of the t test above, it can be concluded that there is a significant influence between locus of control and the work environment because the significant value is less than 0.05 while work conflict has a significance value of 0.053, so it has no significant effect on employee performance.

Then the output of the F test is known that $F_{count} > F_{table}$, namely $42.589 > 2.870$ with a probability value of $0.000 < 0.05$. This shows that locus of control, work environment and work conflict variables have a joint effect on employee performance. then the result of the test for the coefficient of determination is the adjusted-R2 value of 0.762. It can be

concluded that the ability of locus of control variables, work environment and work conflict in explaining employee performance is 76.2%, while the remaining 23.8% is explained by other variables that are not examined in this study.

4.2 Discussion

Based on the results of tests that have been carried out using the SPSS 25.0 tool, the results show that locus of control, work environment have a positive and significant effect on employee performance, while work conflict has an effect on employee performance at PT Bank Central Asia Kcu Solo. Based on the results of the t test, it is known that work conflict affects employee performance. Thus the hypothesis which states that there is an influence between work conflict on employee performance is rejected. Conflict is one thing that must be avoided in the world of work. The existence of conflict can reduce the comfort of an employee at work. Because conflicts must be prevented and resolved as quickly as possible so that they do not have a negative impact on performance,

Although work conflict does not affect employee performance, Waruwu (2018) states that work conflict is important to pay attention to and keep low and controlled. It is known that the work environment affects employee performance. Thus the hypothesis which states that there is an influence between the work environment on employee performance is accepted. The influence of the work environment on employee performance has a positive direction, so that the better the work environment, the employee's performance will also increase. that locus of control affects employee performance, based on the results of this study in line with research conducted by Sihaloho and Siregar (2019) where the work environment has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

According to Sihaloho and Siregar (2019) there is a close relationship between a comfortable work environment and the quality of employee performance. Cintia and Gilang's research (2018) also shows that the work environment has a significant effect on employee performance. Thus the hypothesis which states that there is an influence between self-control (locus of control) on employee performance is accepted. The influence of locus of control on employee performance has a positive relationship direction so that the higher the locus of control, the employee's performance will increase, based on the results of this study in line with research conducted by Isnanto et al. (2020) and Wirani (2013) which state that locus of control has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research on the influence of locus of control, work environment and work conflict on employee performance, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Based on the results of the t test it is known that the locus of control variable has a tcount (3.720) greater than ttable (2.028) and a significance value of $0.001 < 0.05$. The first hypothesis (H1) is accepted, so it can be concluded that locus of control influences employee performance. This means that the higher the locus of control, the employee's performance will increase.
2. Based on the results of the t test it is known that the work environment variable has a tcount (4.484) greater than ttable (2.028) and a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$. The second hypothesis (H2) is accepted, so it can be concluded that the work environment influences employee performance. This means that the better and more comfortable the work environment, the higher the performance of employees.
3. Based on the results of the t test it is known that the work conflict variable has a tcount (-2.001) smaller than ttable (2.028) and a significance value of $0.053 > 0.05$. The third hypothesis (H3) is rejected, so it can be concluded that work conflict has no effect on employee performance. This means that the level of work conflict does not affect employee performance.

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